

CARE FOR STUDENTS WITH DEPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The intensity and the difference between the material and spiritual needs of youth are the most common factors that cause depression at a young age. **Purpose:** To analyze and evaluate the presence or absence of depression among students of two elementary schools in the Municipality of Gjakova. **Methodology:** The population was 200 students from eighth grade (56.5% female & 43.5% male) from the primary school “Zekeria Rexha” and “Mustafa Bakija” in Gjakova (100 students per institution). The survey was conducted during March-April 2019. **Results:** 97 (98.5%) students lived in the city. 105 (52.5%) students stated that sometimes they are upset, 57 (28.5%) students are not happy in life, and 76 (38%) students are worried about their future. 20 (10%) students declare that they will they will commit suicide as soon as the opportunity arises, while another 20 (10%) would like to die. Lack of interest in learning and physical activities, malnutrition, insomnia are some of the factors that are affecting the loss of their positive energy. **Conclusions:** Coordination and organization of activities between the MoH and MEST on health education, workshops and research aimed at preventing youth depression, as well as creating opportunities to engage in every school a psychologist and sociologist. Teachers and parents need to work together to bring children to school. At the same time, the media should be encouraged to develop editorial policies in favor of health education for the prevention of depression.

Keywords: Youth, students, school, teachers, parents, depression, etc.

1. Care for students with depression

Discussion about depression, the factors that cause it and ways to treat it has been recently added. Intensity, the difference between material and spiritual needs in individuals, with their balancing are the most common factors that cause depression at a young age. Except of damaging health, depression is a factor that damages or even diminishes the productivity of youth achievement.

Experience has shown that intervention of institutional or individual factors can mitigate or prevent the effects of depression. Young people who are sociable have elevated self-confidence, emotional support, and leadership. A number of studies show that teenagers do not sleep enough. As a result, they have poorer school performance and their health is damaged. A new study shows that parents can help teenagers to increase their hours of sleep by controlling the time they are exposed to light.

These young people who do not develop positive relationships with peers are at higher risk of developing problems such as delinquency, substance abuse, and depression (Simmon., R., Conger, R., and Wu, C., 1992). The American Academy of Medicine points out that teenagers need 8-10 hours of sleep each night, but many young people sleep only 7 hours or less. This affects school outcomes, mood, behavior and health. In terms of the poorest countries and those in transition, depression has an increased presence and the necessity of its treatment must be an important function and an integral part of society's responsibilities.

It is known that depression is a problem that is perhaps less known by young people, as sudden change in mood and behavior are considered more like normal teenage behavior manifestations. But often depression disorder comes precisely at this stage of life and is associated with a combination of factors.

In one of the recent psychobiological studies on a group of teenagers, they have found several genetic and psychosocial variables that play a role in the context of depression. Depression comes in many forms, just as is the case with other diseases such as heart disease.

The role of family and society in people with depression is enormous. Most important is help, advice to go to a psychiatrist. Anxiolytic disorders, depression and mood disorders are among the most common mental health problems among youth. Half the cases of mental disorders begin before the age of 14. Most young people suffer unnecessarily, unable to access appropriate resources for recognition, support and treatment. These young people are ignored and exposed to a high risk of abuse, indifference, suicide, alcohol and other drug abuse, school failure, violent and criminal activity, mental illness at adulthood and impulsive behavior that endanger health.

The purpose of this study was to analyze and evaluate the presence or absence of depression among students of "Zekeria Rexha" Elementary School and "Mustafa Bakija" Elementary School in Municipality of Gjakova. Another purpose was to recognize and compare the findings presented by the students of these two schools, thus making us aware and understand the situation reflected in general, a purpose that would provide understanding of the needs for the support of these young people

by the institutions and society in general. What should drive us to work in this regard is that depression in young people is of great importance and as such is a contemporary problem, so we need to use effective varieties and techniques in preventing depression in young people.

2. Methodology

The method used in this study is a partial method; making analysis and realistic examination of the circumstances in which students are located, giving their opinions about the problems in learning, collaboration, activities and their feelings in society. The obtained data were grouped according to the questions asked, statistical parameters were calculated, data were presented through tables and charts and finally the analysis and discussion of the obtained results. This study was attended by 200 students of 8th grade (56.5% female and 43.5% male) from the primary school "Zekeria Rexha" and "Mustafa Bakija" in Gjakova (100 students per institution). The study was conducted during March - April 2019.

3. Data collection and analysis

The data collection procedures are relevant and accurate through measurements of the numerical expression variables to represent the quantity and the difference. Data collection was conducted through an anonymous questionnaire consisting of 16 questions. Data processing and analysis was performed using the following software: Microsoft Excel, Microsoft Word and SPSS. All data collected are thoroughly analyzed, maintaining absolute reliability and always based on ethical principles.

4. Results

The respondents were 200 students (teenagers), where 100 students were from elementary school, Zekeria Rexha "and 100 other students from elementary school, Mustafa Bakija" in Gjakova. Of these students interviewed, 56.5% were female and 43.5% male. According to the place of residence, 98.5% of the interviewed students lived in the city, while 1.5% lived in the village.

The boredom among the youth of these two schools turns out to be different, as the boredom turns out to be more pronounced among the students of elementary school "Zekeria Rexha" in 72 (36%) students, while among the students of elementary school "Mustafa Bakija" is found in 53 (26.5%) students. According to the chi-squared test = 8.2514, value $p = .0161$, we are dealing with a significant score ($p < .05$) for students of both schools. (Table no.1)

Tab.no.1 - Boredom in Youth

Modalities	P.Sch. Zekeria Rexha		P.Sch. Mustafa Bakija		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I'm not bored	28	28.0	47	47.0	75	37.5
Sometimes'm bored	62	62.0	43	43.0	105	52.5
Very upset	10	10.0	10	10.0	20	10.0
TOTAL	100	100	100	100	200	100

When it comes to young people's thinking about the future, 40% of students from "Zekeria Rexha" are worried about the future and do not expect anything from the future, while 36% of students from "Mustafa Bakija" are concerned about the future and do not expect anything from the future. According to the chi-squared test = 8.251, value $p = .0161$, we find that we have a significant result ($p < .05$). (Graph no. 1)

Graph no.1 - Opinion of the youth for the future

How satisfied are young people for the things that they do. The students of both schools presented almost the same situations and opinions, as 27 students from "Zekerija Rexha" school stated that they are not satisfied as before, while 30 students from "Mustafa Bakija" school share the same opinion with their peers. of "Zekeria Rexha" school. According to the chi-squared test = 2.18, value $p = .334$, there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Table no. 2)

Tab.no.2 – Young people's thinking about the pleasures they make

Modalities	P.Sch. Zekeria Rexha		P.Sch. Mustafa Bakija		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I have the usual pleasure	73	73.0	70	70.0	143	71.5
I do not enjoy myself as much as before	15	15.0	22	22.0	37	18.5
I have no pleasure now	12	12.0	8	8.0	20	10.0
TOTAL	100	100.0	100	100.0	200	100.0

Adolescence is the most likely age to make mistakes, distortions, but if we compare the teenagers of these schools we can say that they do not feel guilty about anything, despite their actions, because they are of age prone to creating the idea of changing themselves and the process. In "Zekeria Rexha" school about 43% of students stated

that they feel guilty, while at “Mustafa Bakija” school, 36% of students stated that they felt guilty. According to the chi-square test = 1.12, value $p = .571$, there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Graph no. 2)

Graph no.2 - Young people's perception of guilt

Young people's interest in people and activities, at 30% of “Zekeria Rexha” students declare that they are less interested or have lost interest in people and activities, while the same situation is reported by 24% of “Mustafa.Bakija” students. According to the chi-square test = 3.156, value $p = .206$, it turns out that there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Graph no. 3)

Graph no.3 - The interest of young people for the people and activities

One of the questions asked was how much young people trust themselves. Here we find that 83% namely 87% feel comfortable with themselves just as they did before. Whereas 17% of the students from “Zekeria Rexha” school stated that they do not feel confident as before, while 13% of the students from “Mustafa Bakija” school share the same opinion. According to the chi-square test = 0.654, value $p = .721$, it turns out that there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Graph no. 4)

Graph no.4 - Young people's confidence in themselves

How much are young people self-critical, it turns out that 58% of students from "Zekeria Rexha" school do not criticize themselves more than usual, while the same action is presented by 60% of the students from "Mustafa.Bakija" school. Whereas in terms of self-criticism more than usual and for everything that young people do, it turns out to be 42% among the students of "Zekeria Rexha" school and 40% among the students from "Mustafa Bakija" school. According to the chi-square test = 7.028, value $p = .029$, there is a significant difference ($p < .05$). (Graph no. 5)

Graph no.5 - How young are self-critical

Regarding concerns of young people, it turns out that 75% of students of "Zekeria Rexha" school stated that they do not have any concerns and are patient, with almost the same result is being reported in 76% of students of "Mustafa Bakija" school. Regarding the concerns and being impatient it turns out to be 25% among the students of "Zekeria Rexha" school and 24% among the students of "Mustafa Bakija" school. According to the chi-square test = 1.033, value $p = .596$, it turns out that there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Graph no. 6)

Graph no.6 - Youth Concern

How irritable the young people are is shown in the table no.3, where 64% of the students from "Zekeria Rexha" are frustrated almost all the time and this situation occurs inwith 51% of students from "Mustafa Bakija" school. According to the chi-square test = 8.975, vlue $p = .029$, there is a significant difference ($p < .05$).

Tab. No.3 – Youth Inequality

Modalities	P.Sch. Zekeria Rexha		P.Sch. Mustafa Bakija		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I'm not nervous	34	34.0	49	49.0	83	41.5
I'm a little more nervous than usual	43	43.0	35	35.0	78	39.0
I'm much more nervous than usual	15	15.0	15	15.0	30	15.0
All the time I'm nervous	8	8.0	1	1.0	9	4.5
TOTAL	100	100	100	100	200	100

Thinking about punishment, according to the statements of students from “Zekeria. Rexha ”turns out to be present in 20% of them, while 25% turns out to be present in students from“ Mustafa Bakija ”school. According to the chi-square test = 1.033, value $p = .596$, it turns out that there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Table no.4)

Tab.no.4 - Young people's opinion of punishment

Modalities	P.Sch. Zekeria Rexha		P.Sch. Mustafa Bakija		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I don't seem to be punished	80	80.0	75	75.0	155	77.5
I agree to be punished	16	16.0	23	23.0	39	19.5
I'm already punished	4	4.0	2	2.0	6	3.0
TOTAL	100	100	100	100	200	100

Young people's thinking about suicide, in both groups of students from two schools, 90% state that they never think about it, but it is disturbing the fact that 10% of the students from “Zekeria Rexha ”school and 10% of students from“ Mustafa Bakija ”school declares that they wish to die or will make such a move as soon as they are given the opportunity. According to the chi-square test = 0.8, value $p = .670$, there is no significant difference ($p < .05$). (Graph no.7)

Graph no.7 – Young people's opinion of suicide

Conclusions

Based on the findings and results obtained in this study, we can conclude that: boredom among the youth of these two schools is found to be present in 62.5% of students, while youth thinking about the future is also another concern, as 40.5% of students in both schools see no future and perspective in their lives. Satisfaction not at the appropriate level is reported in 28.5% of students. Adolescence is the age most prone to make mistakes, deformities, and when we analyze the findings we find that 39.5% of students stated that they feel guilty. Young people's interest in people and activities, 27% of students are less interested or have lost interest in people and activities. Reliability turns out to be fluctuating in 30% of students. How much self-critical are young people, it turns out that 41% of students are self-critical more than usual about everything they do. Concern was another influencing factor where 24.5% of students report being anxious and impatient, which makes them more irritable and this is found in 57.5% of students in both schools. Thinking about punishment, according to students' statements, turns out to be present in 22.5% of them. Since adolescence is a defining age for a number of important characteristics to come in the future, one must look very carefully as most of the students interviewed do not feel themselves to be a failure, despite the economic and social difficulties they face in their families. Another problem faced by young people is the situation of post-traumatic stress in their families, presented as a result of the recent war situation in Kosovo, a condition that is adversely affecting the health and life of the interviewed youth. Also, sleeping and eating problems are almost the same among students in both schools. In the absence of commitments, physical activities, and malnutrition, young people can have different complaints and loss of their energy. Considering all these situations and adding other factors such as lack of economic and social conditions, prejudices from society, inability to integrate into society and other health related problems to some of the youth, were some of the factors highlighted by young people and that makes them think about suicide, which is a disturbing fact of the students' statement from both schools, where 10% of them wanted to die or would do so as soon as they were given the opportunity.

Based on the findings and conclusions, we can propose:

- The Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Education Science and Technology to increase the level of cooperation, at the same time to coordinate and organize activities for health education, workshops and research in order to prevent youth depression,
- Ensuring the participation of youth in education/training on the prevention of depression,
- Treating young people suffering from anxiety and depression,

- Supporting young people who have problems with post-traumatic stress in their families,
- Creating opportunities to engage psychologist and sociologist in every school,
- Teachers and parents must cooperate about the behavior of children at school and home.
- Encourage the media to develop editorial policies in favor of health education for the prevention of depression and educational programs

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